
Spheres of the security strategy within the competences of the Košice self-government region

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Abstract

The article deals with the issue of security and variability of competencies in the security strategy of the regional self-government, such as the Košice self-governing region. The article theoretically processes the current position of the regional self-government in the context of procedures and creation of security policy, especially in the management of the regional Security Council.

Key words: security, self-governing region, security council, competencies.

Introduction

The growing issue of the territorial-administrative and regional division of Slovakia in the context of increasing sovereignty and autonomy in decision-making about financial and security operations are the main reasons for processing this article. The management of public finances, especially in the modern history of modern democratic states, becomes an essential matter of public affairs management. Adjectives such as transparent, efficient, effective, economically spent financial means for managing public goods and services have now become established not only in the vocabulary of politicians, public officials, elected representatives, but also civil activists, the non-profit sector, or even ordinary laymen and “civilians”. What was once neglected even in the highest spheres of state management, today we commonly find it in the functioning of a traditional household. It is precisely to the public imperatives such as the aforementioned transparency, efficiency, efficiency and economy that nowadays, in the 21st century, the concept of security is added more and more urgently. It is this that completes the overall security profile, that the resources necessary for the functioning of areas such as health care, education, defense, road communications, the environment and many others, coming mainly from the wallets of citizens and entrepreneurs, will be safe even in the hands of the ruling set and will be spent to the maximum extent possible for the purposes, for which there was a societal demand in the country.

A self-governing region takes care of the all-round development of its territory and the needs of its inhabitants in the exercise of self-government. At the same time, it mainly ensures the creation and implementation of the program of social, economic and cultural development of the territory of the self-governing region, plans activities related to the territory of the self-governing region, approves territorial plans of the regions, makes effective use of local human, natural and other resources, carries out its own investment activities and business activities in order to ensure the needs of the residents of the self-governing region and the development of the self-governing region, participates in the protection of the environment, creates prerequisites for the optimal arrangement of mutual relations between residential units, manages the provision of social services in the region and cooperates with municipalities and other legal entities and natural persons in the construction of facilities designed to provide social services, creates the conditions for the development of health care, the development of education and training, especially in secondary schools, creates the conditions for the presentation of cultural values and cultural activities and takes care of the protection

of the monument fund, coordinates the development of tourism, sports and the care of children and youth, and performs other functions established special laws. The Košice self-governing region (KSK) is also the founder of budget and contribution organizations, and in this way processes 70 schools and school facilities, 13 social service facilities, 20 cultural organizations, or other companies for the management of road assets or technical and social infrastructure of the region. The region coordinates public suburban transport on its territory or solves the issue of crime prevention. creates the conditions for the presentation of cultural values and cultural activities and takes care of the protection of the monument fund, coordinates the development of tourism, sports and the care of children and youth, and performs other functions established by special laws. The Košice self-governing region is also the founder of budget and contribution organizations, and in this way processes 70 schools and school facilities, 13 social service facilities, 20 cultural organizations, or other companies for the management of road assets or technical and social infrastructure of the region. The region coordinates public suburban transport on its territory or solves the issue of crime prevention. creates the conditions for the presentation of cultural values and cultural activities and takes care of the protection of the monument fund, coordinates the development of tourism, sports and the care of children and youth, and performs other functions established by special laws. The Košice self-governing region is also the founder of budget and contribution organizations, and in this way processes 70 schools and school facilities, 13 social service facilities, 20 cultural organizations, or other companies for the management of road assets or technical and social infrastructure of the region. The region coordinates public suburban transport on its territory or solves the issue of crime prevention. sports and the care of children and youth and performs other functions established by special laws. The Košice self-governing region is also the founder of budget and contribution organizations, and in this way processes 70 schools and school facilities, 13 social service facilities, 20 cultural organizations, or other companies for the management of road assets or technical and social infrastructure of the region. The region coordinates public suburban transport on its territory or solves the issue of crime prevention. sports and the care of children and youth and performs other functions established by special laws. The Košice self-governing region is also the founder of budget and contribution organizations, and in this way processes 70 schools and school facilities, 13 social service facilities, 20 cultural organizations, or other companies for the management of road assets or technical and social infrastructure of the region. The region coordinates public suburban transport on its territory or solves the issue of crime prevention.

All the mentioned areas and spheres of competence influence of the Košice regional self-government have a significant element of security, which we will discuss in the next few lines from the perspective of several areas of the security strategy implemented in the management of processes in the regional self-government.

Results

Various forms of procedures in the area of human, property and information security in the competence solution of the selected territorial self-governing unit – Košice self-governing region

In connection with the ongoing extraordinary pandemic situation on the territory of the Slovak Republic as well as with the conflict in Ukraine in 2022, the Košice Self-Governing Region took measures against the spread of the new virus and at the same time took measures in connection with the situation in Ukraine, which directly affected the Košice Self-Governing Region. to emergency situations in the country, the Office of the Košice Self-governing Region held regular meetings of the Crisis Staff, which evaluated the situations that had arisen and, within its competences, adapted other measures to solve them.

Since the Košice self-governing region also includes school, social and cultural facilities and the Road Administration, the measures taken to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 disease as well as the arrival of refugees from Ukraine have had a direct impact on the functioning of these organizations.

The activity of the Košice self-governing region in 2022 was defined in terms of security mainly to take preventive measures to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 disease and to solve the situation in Ukraine related to the influx of refugees and to fulfill the tasks associated with them. Košice self-governing region responded through the measures taken, which resulted from the meetings of the Crisis Staff of the District Office in Košice, as well as from the meetings of the Crisis Staff of the Košice self-governing region. Their main goal was to protect the citizens of the region to the maximum extent and mitigate the impact of the pandemic and to solve the situation with the influx of refugees from Ukraine, with their placement in short-term or long-term accommodation. In this context, the Košice self-governing region actively cooperated with the relevant central state administration bodies, the District Office in Košice, as well as with other self-governing regions.

In the field of health care, the Košice self-governing region regularly issues operating permits to institutional and outpatient health care providers whose place of business is tied to the territory of the region. Current guidelines issued by the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic as well as the Public Health Office of the Slovak Republic were sent to health care providers through the e-VUC application, so that every doctor has available all the current rules regarding the protection of patients' health when providing health care. Even in the course of 2022, the Košice self-governing region ensured the distribution of antigen tests to individual outpatient health care providers in accordance with their requirements. These were tests from the State Material Reserves. The doctor of the self-governing region participated in working negotiations related to the current pandemic situation, at the same time, in cooperation with the Department of Health of the Košice self-governing region, he corrected and updated measures and guidelines for all members and employees of the Office of the Košice self-governing region, depending on the development of the pandemic situation. The press department of the Košice self-governing region further informed the population of the Košice region on the website of the Office of the Košice self-governing region and on social networks about the current measures taken. At the same time, the representatives of the Košice self-governing region intensively communicated and cooperated with the Regional Office of Public Health in solving measures to protect the health of the population. The Košice self-governing region continued to ensure the vaccination process during 2022 – the third and, subsequently, if interested, the fourth dose of the vaccine. During January 2022, a total of 29,714 vaccines were administered as part of the vaccination process, which was ensured by the Košice self-governing region through large-capacity vaccination centers in Košice, Michalovce, Spišská Nová Ves and through the on-site vaccination service. During the following months, interest in vaccination gradually decreased, vaccination centers were suppressed and vaccination days were reduced. A total of 4,204 vaccines were administered during February 2022, 840 vaccines were administered during March 2022, 191 vaccines were administered during April 2022, and 104 vaccines were administered in May 2022. At the end of May 2022, vaccination against the disease COVID-19 through the county was completed.

The Košice self-governing region, as a subject of crisis management, was actively involved in helping citizens from Ukraine who had to leave their homes due to the war conflict. Immediately after the outbreak of the war, the Infoline of the Košice self-governing region was established for the residents who sought refuge in Slovakia before the war to help Ukraine. The toll-free number was available 24/7. It was operated by volunteers from the Volunteer Center of the Košice Region, with whom the callers spoke in Slovak and Ukrainian. The line primarily served war refugees. Here they learned more about accommodation options, transport links, humanitarian aid, as well as the conditions for granting asylum or ensuring school attendance for school-age children. The line was also intended for all those who were interested in helping war refugees in any way. Contact was also possible via e-mail. The Košice self-governing region opened asylum centers, provided shuttle transport from border crossings, provided basic humanitarian aid and established contact points on the Slovakian-Ukrainian border in Vyšné Nemec and in the village of Veľké Slemence. The information point was also made available at the railway stations in Košice and Michalovce. Volunteers from the Volunteer Center of the Košice Region provided information to the war

refugees. At the railway and bus stations in Košice and at the railway station in Michalovce, the county set up information booths, where war refugees received basic information about accommodation options, volunteers helped them find the necessary transport connection or buy a ticket. Due to the situation regarding the arrival of war refugees, the Košice self-governing region established a vaccination site in the container town during the 10th week of 2022. It was located at the Červená Hviezda swimming pool in Košice, near the railway and bus stations. This vaccination site served temporarily instead of the vaccination cubicle directly in the railway station building in Košice, which was always open on Fridays. Due to low interest, this service was later discontinued. Part of the premises, and later at the end of March 2022, the entire gymnasium of SOŠ Ostrovského 1 in Košice, which was used for vaccinations, was repurposed for the storage of humanitarian aid for war refugees. Vaccination remained at the original address, but was moved to the associated premises of the building. A special reservation system for accommodation was created for war refugees, which was available on the website www.ukrajnask.sk and was about the possibility of accommodation in accommodation facilities within the jurisdiction of the region. All the necessary information was published on the website in question in Slovak as well as in Ukrainian. At the same time, the website was used for the registration of volunteers who were not indifferent to the situation caused by the war in Ukraine and wanted to help. This specially prepared website also offered the possibility of reporting available accommodation capacities within households. It was important help for refugees who were looking for a temporary facility with a roof over their heads for themselves and their loved ones. Those interested could register via a form and were subsequently contacted by a county employee to arrange assistance. The website also offered the registration of transport capacity assistance, i.e. if someone had a means of transport, time and willingness to help, he was able to transport refugees before the war conflict from a place near the border or from another place to their destination (e.g. accommodation). The Košice self-governing region provided 25 temporary accommodation facilities that were available. More than 6,000 war refugees were accommodated in them. More than 1200 beds were available. Tons of humanitarian aid of various kinds were brought to the humanitarian aid warehouses. Humanitarian aid was subsequently redistributed to places where it was needed (border, accommodation facilities, etc.). Volunteers played an important role and extremely demanding physical work in storage, sorting, registration and removal. Anyone who wanted to help could also do so through the Foundation of the Košice self-governing region. It was possible to contribute a voluntary sum of money to a transparent account. Financial donations were used to buy the missing basic necessities and for additional help connected with the stay with us. Through the “Who will help Ukraine” initiative, citizens could donate any amount, 100% of the collected money was intended for humanitarian aid in Ukraine, or for helping Ukrainian men and women who sought safety on our territory.

In order for help to foreigners to be targeted and effective, the Košice self-governing region has joined forces with organizations and associations such as the DEDO Foundation, the League for Human Rights, Mareena, Human in Danger, ETP Slovakia, Everyone for the Family, Dorka, Oáza – hope for a new life and the Archdiocese Charity Košice. The Integration Center of the Košice Region was established under the auspices of the Košice Self-Governing Region. To this day, the center provides help, for example, in filling out forms and applications, in teaching Slovak, and in orientation on the labor market. In addition, he provides advice on leisure activities. Its goal is to offer the widest possible portfolio of services in one place. Foreigners can book an appointment in person, by phone or email, the center at Strojárska 3 in Košice is open every working day from 8:30 a.m. to 4:00 p.m.

Secondary Industrial Transport School, Hlavná 113, Košice, in cooperation with the Košice self-governing region, created a uniform form – customs declaration – in Ukrainian, English and Slovak languages. It is essential for transporting humanitarian aid to war-torn Ukraine. The financial administrations of Slovakia and Ukraine originally used different forms. Also, thanks to the region, it is enough for the sender of goods to Ukraine to make an electronic entry on one form. The new uniform form significantly shortens and simplifies the entire customs declaration process. It is

suitable for natural and legal persons and is accepted by both countries. It is available in the format PDF with the possibility of electronic filling.

The Košice Self-Governing Region also participates in the provision of social care and services to the most vulnerable citizens placed in social service facilities, not only within the scope of establishment of the Košice Self-Governing Region, but also with all social service providers in the territory of the Košice Region.

In these facilities, he actively monitored the situation in 2022, took microbiological smears and evaluated them, regularly disinfected the premises of social service homes, tested employees and clients of the facilities, monitored the current health conditions of employees and clients daily, processed a number of analyzes and statistical data. Even in the monitored period, he continued to distribute antigen tests and protective equipment to all social service facilities in the region, including non-public providers.

During the period of the pandemic in 2022, secondary schools and school facilities followed the instructions of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic. From September 1, 2021, schools followed the so-called school traffic lights, which were published on the website Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic, which establishes the basic operating conditions of schools and school facilities, including the specifics of compliance with anti-epidemiological measures and recommendations during the pandemic. After the winter holidays from 10.1.2022, school operations were resumed in schools and school facilities in accordance with the valid school traffic lights, which were regularly updated by the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic according to the situation. The operation of schools and school facilities was not restricted across the board.

Decision of the Minister of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic No. 2022/10917:1-A1810 dated 18.01.2022 with effect from 19.01.2022, school activities according to § 28 par. 16, § 30 par. 6 and § 33 par. 12 of the School Act could only take place under the conditions established by the currently effective decrees of the Public Health Office of the Slovak Republic, which mandated measures in the event of a threat to public health, in particular measures to restrict operations and measures to restrict mass events. At the same time, it was possible to implement exchange programs for secondary school students according to the Education Act.

For the purposes of informing the founder, in January 2022 the Office of the Košice Self-Governing Region created an application to facilitate the provision of information related to the Chairman's Instruction No. 25/2020, by which county schools and school facilities were to report data on the number of pupils in face-to-face and distance education, as well as data on the number of confirmed pupils/employees with the disease COVID-19, the number of pupils/employees in quarantine due to suspicion and the number of pupils/ employees who are exempt from quarantine. After testing, the application began to be actively used from February 9, 2022.

Decision of the Minister of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic No. 2022/12509:1-A1810 dated 02/25/2022 with effect from 02/28/2022, a declaration of symptom-free status was submitted for the purposes of teaching at school and operating school facilities. At the same time, Decision no. 2022/12509:1-A1810 was amended so that the operation of school catering facilities for diners who are not children, pupils or employees of the school in which school teaching takes place in the school or school facilities that are in operation was only allowed in the scope of food and drinks.

At the same time, during school hours, the school director according to § 50 par. 5 of the School Act could hereby grant leave to pupils of one class or to pupils of several classes due to the suspicion of the occurrence of the COVID-19 disease for more than five days with the consent of the founder. Such a leave was considered an extraordinary interruption of school teaching at the school. In the event that operations were restricted or interrupted in relation to one class or several classes based on the measures of the competent authorities due to the disease of COVID-19 or the suspicion of the disease of COVID-19, this was considered an extraordinary interruption of school teaching in the school or in the school facility.

Schools were obliged to notify the Ministries of Education, Science, Research and Sports. Slovak Republic data on children, pupils and employees in relation to the occurrence of the disease COVID-19 at school and on the method of ensuring school teaching during a crisis situation to the extent determined by the Ministry every Monday and without delay in case of any change in the situation at school due to the occurrence of COVID-19.

Decision of the Minister of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic No. 2022/12509:2-A1810 dated 03/03/2022 with effect from 03/04/2022, the operation of school catering facilities within the scope of food and drink consumption until the end of the emergency situation was also made possible for members of the armed forces of the Slovak Republic.

Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sports. On May 10, 2022, the Slovak Republic published Guidelines for a safe environment in schools and school facilities during the COVID-19 pandemic and emergency situations, which is published on the website Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sports SR, which is valid for the duration of the COVID-19 pandemic and the emergency situation at the time when the school traffic light is suspended due to the improving development of the epidemic situation.

In the period from 01/01/2022 to 03/31/2022, suburban regular bus transport was provided by the carrier Eurobus, a.s. based on Decision no. 7872 /2021/OD-51145 and the carrier ARRIVA Michalovce, as and on the basis of Decision no. 7872 /2021/OD-51148. On February 25, 2022, the Košice self-governing region signed new contracts for services in the public interest in suburban regular bus transport valid for 7 years, starting from April 1, 2022. The bus carriers that serve the territory of the Košice self-governing region with suburban bus transport are the following companies: Eurobus, as for the Košice West region (in the Spiš, Gemer and Košice regions) and ARRIVA Michalovce, as for the Košice East region (in the Zemplín, Sobranecko and Medzibodrožie regions).

The contractual bus carrier of the Košice self-governing region, ARRIVA Michalovce, operates regular bus services from the Vyšné Nemecké border crossing to the train station in Michaloviece. Itineraries are available in Slovak and Ukrainian on the website IDS Východ, sro.

Residents from Ukraine could use suburban bus services in the Košice region free of charge. In connection with the extraordinary situation on the Slovak-Ukrainian state border, caused by the military conflict in Ukraine, the Košice self-governing region provided free transportation to all Ukrainian citizens who were heading to the territory of Slovakia. The free transportation concerned both contracted bus carriers of the Košice self-governing region. Ukrainian citizens were provided with free transport upon proof of identity card or passport.

The Košice self-governing region cooperated with IDS Východ, s.r.o. on the harmonization and coordination of the public transport offer during 2022 and also in connection with the coordination of extraordinary tariff and transport measures in connection with the transport of war refugees from Ukraine (zero fare) and the adjustment of the conditions of zero fare, cooperation in connection with new contracts for services in the public interest in suburban regular bus transport.

The Department of Social Affairs of the Košice Self-Governing Region is a member of a multidisciplinary work team (of child protection and social guardianship bodies, Police Department units, prosecutor's office, courts, schools and medical facilities, non-profit organizations, municipalities and self-governing regions) called NP Support for the Protection of Children from Violence, whose goal is mainly to create a communication mechanism between the affected entities and to acquire and expand the knowledge of the involved workers about the roles and activities of individual entities, to deepen the mutual cooperation of institutions/entities participating in the protection of children from violence in order to more effectively solve the issue of protecting children from violence, a space for joint search solutions in the issue of protecting children from violence in view of local needs, shortcomings, assessment of cooperation, established procedures, measures and mechanisms leading to effective cooperation between individual participating entities.

During of 2022, 2 multidisciplinary working meetings were held in the Košice Region, the topic of which was mainly the current events in the system of protecting children from violence from

the point of view of the institutions involved, informing about upcoming activities within the NP Supporting the protection of children from violence and important information in the field of child protection against violence and current possibilities for preventing peer violence such as bullying, cyberbullying, etc.

In May 2022, an online education entitled “Methodology for detecting child abuse, or of domestic violence”, where the consequences of experiences of domestic violence, problems of contact between the child and the parent after the separation of the parental couple, the best interest of the child in the context of custody disputes were mainly addressed. Non-public providers who provide social services in the shelter and among the recipients of social assistance participated in the online education. services are children.

The Department of Social Affairs of the Košice self-governing region has also established cooperation with organizations working in the field of human trafficking prevention – the IOM Migration Information Center and the Information Center for Combating Human Trafficking and Crime Prevention. In March 2022, after the outbreak of the conflict in Ukraine, informational materials focused on protection against human trafficking were distributed to facilities where the Košice self-governing region provided accommodation for emigrants.

The Košice self-governing region is the owner of roads II. and III. classes on its territory, except for sections passing through the city of Košice and through customs areas. In total, this represents 558 km of roads II. class and 1372 km of roads III. class, as well as 660 bridge objects. The Košice self-governing region ensures planning, preparation and modernization of the road network. For the purpose of road management, their regular and winter maintenance, the contribution organization Správa ciest KSK was established.

Road Administration KSK is a subject of economic mobilization and as a road administrator II. and III. class in the territory of the Košice self-governing region provides services within the framework of administration, maintenance, repairs, reconstruction and construction of roads and bridges. It is an integral part of critical infrastructure.

During the first half of 2022, it provided services related to the maintenance of roads I., II. and III. class and the implementation of several repairs and reconstructions of roads and bridges also began. Among the most important current constructions of the lot: Reconstruction of the bridge near Sírník, reconstruction of the Marge any bridge, II/549 Pačanský kopec, Hačava – Háj and Rudňany – Poráč.

In the field of civil protection, the Košice self-governing region cooperated with state administration and local self-government authorities in providing the necessary documents, planning, ensuring and creating conditions for dealing with extraordinary events within the framework of its scope and competences.

Košice self-governing region he methodically managed the preparation for self-defense and mutual aid in these organizations. The organizations also fulfilled the tasks and measures of civil protection established by the relevant district authorities. The Košice self-governing region has developed a Crisis Plan and its own planning documentation according to the instructions of the Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic in electronic form in the specific application program EPSIS® JISHM, as well as in paper form. Crisis plans are drawn up in accordance with the decree of the Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic, which implements some provisions of the Act on Economic Mobilization.

In the first half of 2022, the Košice self-governing region, through the foundation of the Košice self-governing region, also carried out activities to support the social stability of vulnerable groups.

The Košice self-governing region strives in emergency situations to maintain security to the maximum extent possible with all personnel, transport, material, technical and energy equipment at its disposal, to fulfill tasks and measures aimed at the defense of the state, the preservation of its security, the protection of life and employee health and property protection according to Constitutional Act No. 227/2002 Coll. on State Security in Time of War, State of War, State of Emergency and State of Emergency and according to other legal standards, in the field of crisis management, economic mobilization and civil protection of the population.

Conclusions

Regional self-government, as a public administration body that is close to the population, fulfills tasks that the government is unable to provide in crisis situations, not because it does not want to, but the proximity of the self-governing region makes the regional unit an indispensable part in crisis situations, as it was during the coronavirus pandemic and later also during the vaccination against the COVID-19 infection, where the regions carried out vaccination of the population based on the authorization of the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic. In the Slovak Republic, the currently ongoing war conflict in Ukraine hit the Košice self-governing region the most, where the influx of refugees was directed to Košice in the first three weeks, and the region ensured the coordination of refugees through the Volunteer Center of the Košice Region, or humanitarian aid by setting up humanitarian warehouses. school facilities, especially dormitories and gymnasiums of the Košice self-governing region became emergency accommodation for refugees for a while. The Košice self-governing region ensured the transport of refugees from the borders through its carriers. Several areas of competence under the responsibility of the Košice regional self-government thus fulfilled the essence of security procedures aimed at protecting people, health, property, and technical and social infrastructure.

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